

Seismic Fragility Analysis of Underground Tunnel Buried in Rock

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ABSTRACT:

This paper presents a brief review of the existing seismic vulnerability assessment of tunnels. In particular, a 3D nonlinear time history analysis is conducted to evaluate the dynamic response of circular shallow tunnels buried in rock, for increasing levels of seismic intensity at the transverse direction of tunnel axis. The seismic performance of the tunnel lining when the effect of soil structure interaction is ignored is evaluated through the construction of fragility curves. Critical analysis has been presented about the current methods of analysis and associated uncertainties on the tunnel integrity. Results denote the significant role of soil condition and input motions in evaluating the performance and response of the tunnel. The derived analytical fragility curves are modified due to differences of soil conditions. The proposed fragility curves clearly highlighted the performance of the tunnel under seismic loads which beneficial for future risk assessment and loss estimation.

Keywords: fragility analysis, seismic loads, tunnel lining, response, performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Underground structures are classified as critical structures and thus require detailed analysis before being designed. Tunnels, for instance, are constructed as part of transportation and utilities infrastructure in urban environments. Considering their importance to the economy and public safety, any instability to the tunnels will be highly detrimental to the performance of the network. Recent experience suggests that tunnels become vulnerable during an earthquake event (e.g. Brito & Lopes 2012; Huo et al. 2005; Hashash et al. 2001). However, very few studies have been carried out in relation to the understanding of the performance of tunnels under unpredictable extreme hazards, like earthquakes.

The aim of this study is order to evaluate probabilistic future performance of tunnels during an earthquake event. This can be done by constructing fragility curves as a representation of probability of damage level of a tunnel subjected to a given seismic hazard. There are four approaches in vogue for constructing the fragility curves; judgmental, analytical, empirical, hybrid, out of which in the present study the analytical approach has been used. This is because (1) the derived fragility curves provide a reduced bias-solution and (2) they can be applied to different structure types and geographical regions where seismic damage observations are insufficient. Traditionally for tunnels, the vulnerability assessment is either based on expert judgment (e.g. NIBS 2004) or by using empirically-derived fragility curves (e.g. ALA 2001). However, recently Argyroudou & Pitilakis (Argyroudou & Pitilakis 2012) proposed a analytical-cum-numerical approach to derive fragility curves for (circular and rectangular) tunnels in alluvial deposits. Tunnel response was predicted under quasi-static conditions, as a function of peak ground acceleration (PGA) at the ground surface (free field condition) by considering the effect of soil structure interaction. Comparisons between analytical and empirical curves highlighted the important role that soil type has on the seismic response of tunnels.

In addition to the effects of soil type and soil-structure interaction, seismic vulnerability is significantly affected by the typology of the tunnel lining. Along these lines, this paper presents a numerical methodology for the construction of fragility curves for shallow circular tunnels in rock. The behaviour of shotcrete tunnel lining is evaluated when the soil-structure interaction effects are ignored.

2. METHODOLOGY

The procedure adopted for the deriving fragility curves for tunnel under ground shaking is presented in Fig. 1.1 and is based on similar previous approaches (see Argyroudis et al. 2014; Argyroudis & Pitilakis 2012; Argyroudis & Kaynia 2014). The dynamic response of the tunnel is evaluated by 3D nonlinear time history dynamic analyses, for increasing levels of seismic intensity at transverse direction of tunnel axis. Typical soil profiles and different seismic input motions are used to account for the effect of soil types and ground motion characteristics on the tunnel response. The fragility curves are constructed as a function of damage level and the type of seismic excitation. This approach allows an evaluation of fragility curves for tunnels, respecting the distinctive features of their geometries, input motion characteristics and soil properties.

Figure 1.1. Procedure for deriving numerical fragility curves for tunnels (modified after Argyroudis & Pitilakis, 2012)

2.1. Definition of Damage States

Table 2.1 shows various damage states which are same as those adopted by Argyroudis & Pitilakis (2012). The damage index (DI) is defined as the ratio between the actual (M) and capacity (M_{Rd}) bending moment of the tunnel cross section. It is assumed that the tunnel's behavior is approximated to that of an elastic beam subjected to deformations imposed by the oscillating surrounding ground due to seismic waves propagating perpendicular to the tunnel axis (Hashash et al. 2001). M is calculated as the combination of static and seismic loads using the Midas GTS NX finite element software (Midas GTS NX 2012), while M_{Rd} is estimated through a section analysis (using Oasys Adsec Ltd 2014) based on the lining material and geometrical properties accounting for the induced axial forces (N) and bending moment (M). Based on previous experience, four damage states (i.e. minor, moderate, extensive and complete) of tunnel lining are considered due to ground shaking.

Table 2.1. Definition of damage states for tunnel lining (Argyroudis & Pitilakis 2012)

Damage state (DS)	Range of damage index (DI)	Central value of damage index
DS1. Minor/slight	$1.0 < M/M_{Rd} \leq 1.5$	1.25
DS2. Moderate	$1.5 < M/M_{Rd} \leq 2.5$	2.00
DS3. Extensive	$2.5 < M/M_{Rd} \leq 3.5$	3.00
DS4. Collapse	$M/M_{Rd} > 3.5$	-

2.2. Estimation of Fragility Curve Parameters

Most of the available fragility curves are usually described by a lognormal probability distribution function (Eqn. 2.1) (NIBS 2004; Argyroudis & Pitilakis 2012; Shinozuka et al. 2000):

$$P_f(ds \geq ds_i | S) = \Phi \left[\frac{1}{\beta_{tot}} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{S}{S_{mi}} \right) \right] \quad (2.1)$$

where $P_f(\cdot)$ is the probability of exceeding a particular damage state, ds , for a given seismic intensity level defined by the earthquake intensity measure S (e.g. PGA), S_{mi} is the median threshold value of S required to cause the i^{th} DS, and β_{tot} is the total lognormal standard deviation. According to Eqn.2.1, the development of fragility curves requires definition of two parameters, S_{mi} and β_{tot} . Thus, the lognormal standard deviation (β_{tot}) is estimated as the root of the sum of the squares of the component dispersions (Eqn. 2.2). Three primary sources of uncertainty are considered (NIBS 2004), namely (1) the definition of DS (β_{ds}), (2) the response and resistance (capacity) of the element (β_C), and (3) the earthquake input motion (demand) (β_D).

$$\beta_{tot} = \sqrt{\beta_{ds}^2 + \beta_C^2 + \beta_D^2} \quad (2.2)$$

As mentioned earlier, in order to determine total lognormal standard deviation (β_{tot}), two crucial parameters β_D and S_{mi} have to be estimated first. Considering the lack of more rigorous estimation, the parameters β_{ds} and β_C are taken as 0.4 and 0.3, respectively (NIBS 2004; Argyroudis & Pitilakis 2012). The last source of uncertainty, associated with seismic demand, is described by the average standard deviation of the damage indices that have been calculated for different input motions at each level of PGA.

3. APPLICATION

3.1. Tunnel and Soil Models

A typical circular shallow tunnel section with: 10m diameter, 1m thick shotcrete lining, 30m overburden depth, measures from the ground surface up to the crown of tunnel lining is considered in the present study (Fig. 3.1), with the main material properties as given in Table 3.1. The selected geometrical and material properties taken from the available previous literature review.

Table 3.1. Material properties of the investigated of tunnel models

	Hardrock	Shotcrete	Rockbolts
Element type	Solid	Shell	Embedded truss
Material model	Mohr-Coulomb	Elastic	Elastic
Material behavior	Drained	-	-
Unit weight [kN/m ³]	25	24	77
Modulus of elasticity, E [kN/m ²]	59×10^5	15×10^6	20×10^7
Poison ratio, ν	0.2	0.2	0.3
Cohesion, c [kN/m ²]	2941	-	-
Friction angle, ϕ [°]	40	-	-
Tensile strength [kPa]	2941	-	-
At-rest earth pressure coefficient, K_0	1.5	-	-
Damping ratio	0.05	0.05	0.05

3.2. Input motions

Seven real acceleration earthquake time histories (Table 3.2) are selected as input motion in outcrop condition for the 3D nonlinear time history soil-tunnel dynamic analyses at the transverse direction of

the tunnel axis (x axis). These selected time histories are scaled from low to high levels of PGA in order to calculate the response of the soil-tunnel systems for increasing levels of seismic intensity.

Table 3.2. Real earthquake records applied to the bedrock of the soil profile

Earthquake Name	Year	PGA (g)	Duration (sec)
Hollywood, Los Angeles	1952	0.059	78.62
Ofunato, Iwate, Japan	2011	0.119	15.87
Loma Prieta, California	1989	0.275	39.98
El Centro Site, California	1940	0.356	53.72
Hokkaido, East Coast, Japan	1994	0.447	60.00
Northridge, Los Angeles, USA	1994	0.604	59.98
Hyogoken South, Japan	1995	0.781	30.00

3.3. Soil-tunnel dynamic Analyses

A 3D dynamic analysis was performed using the Midas GTS NX finite element software (Midas GTS NX 2012), in which the hard rock (classified as soil type A according to EC8) is meshed with 8-noded hexahedron shape solid elements, while the tunnel is modelled with 4-noded quadrilateral shell elements which incorporated embedded truss elements of rock bolts (2-noded). In total, for one particular models for each seismic intensity, the number of nodes, elements, DOFs and equations are 9020, 9745, 32475, and 27243 respectively. The adopted element size is selected in a way that ensures the efficient reproduction of all the waveforms of the whole frequency range under study and the efficient simulation of the circular tunnel-model.

Figure 3.1. Geometry, meshing and boundary conditions of the soil-tunnel system

The acceleration of time history record is applied at the rock outcrop layer of the model. Different boundary conditions, available in literature (Midas GTS NX 2012; BTS & ICE 2004) are considered in this study (see Fig. 3.1). The surface of hard rock was assumed to be flat and free from loadings, while at the bottom of the homogenous hard rock medium which overlaid the rigid bedrock, fixed boundary condition was assumed at x (transverse), y (longitudinal) and z (vertical) axes of the investigated model. However, the front and back faces of the hard rock are allowed to move on x and z but fixed on y . The opposite boundaries are applied on the left and right faces of the hard rock. The input motion is introduced at the base boundary in terms of acceleration time history.

4. COMPARISON AND VALIDATION OF THE NUMERICAL RESULTS

4.1. Moment and Axial Force In Circular Tunnel

In the present study, the influence of the most critical parameters affecting the structural response is determined and critically discussed through parametric sensitivity analysis. The effect on thickness and ground intensity on the obtained moment and axial force of investigated tunnel models is summarized in Figs. 4.1 to 4.3.

Figure 4.1. The maximum bending moment (unit in kNm/m) of the shell element subjected to El Centro earthquake record for two different thicknesses of shotcrete

Figure 4.2. The maximum axial force (unit in kN/m) of the shell element subjected to El Centro earthquake record for two different thicknesses of shotcrete

Figure 4.3. The maximum bending moments and axial forces of the shell element subjected to seven real earthquake record for 100cm thicknesses of shotcrete

The obtained numerical results are compared based on two parameters; thicknesses and ground intensity. It is found that the values of axial force and bending moment for 30cm thickness of tunnel lining are higher than the values obtained for 100cm thickness of the tunnel lining (Figs.4.1 and 4.2) Meanwhile, the higher level of PGA is resulted to the higher value of axial force and bending moment, however this parameter not been attributed to the failure of the lining (ALA 2001) which actually depending on various uncertainties as suggested by Owen and Scholl (1981) and Sharma and Judd (1991) (i.e. typology of tunnels, geological condition and earthquake parameters).

4.2. Fragility curves

The derivation of fragility curves as described in Eqn. 2.1 is based on the construction of diagram of the computed damage indices versus PGA at the ground surface according to the definitions presented in Table 2.1. This can be done by constructing the graph evolution of damage index with increasing earthquake intensity (see Fig.4.4). The graph is constructed by linear regression analysis, considering the natural logarithm of the damage index (lnDI) as the dependent variable and PGA as the independent variable.

Figure 4.4. Evolution of damages with PGA at the ground surface for circular tunnel model

The derived curve referring to typical hard rock soil profiles (classified as soil type A according to EC8) with buried circular shallow tunnel model is compared and validated with previous analytical fragility curves prepared by Argyroudis et al. (2014) and Argyroudis & Ptilakis (2012). Furthermore, the accuracy of obtained results was compared with the other two different types of fragility curves; expert judgement and empirical which were developed by NIBS (2004) in the HAZUS and by ALA (2001) respectively. The representative curves illustrated for minor damage state are shown in Figs. 4.5 to 4.9, together with the parameters of fragility curves in terms of median and standard deviation.

Figure 4.5. Comparison of analytical fragility curves between proposed present study and previous study by Argyroudis & Ptilakis (2012)

Figure 4.6. Comparison of analytical fragility curves between proposed present study and previous study by Argyroudis et al. (2014) for New Tunnel (NT) Construction

Figure 4.7. Comparison of analytical fragility curves between proposed present study and previous study by Argyroudis et al. (2014) for Old Tunnel (OT) Construction

Figure 4.8. Comparison between proposed analytical and previous expert-judgement fragility curves (NIBS 2004) of all types of bored tunnel

Figure 4.9. Comparison between proposed and previous empirical fragility curves (ALA 2001) for both good (GQC) and poor (PQC) quality of construction work of rock tunnel (RT) and soil tunnel (ST)

From Fig.4.5, comparison with the previous analytical fragility curve by Argyroudis & Pitilakis (2012) shows that the exceedance probability of minor damage is expected on the proposed models is higher (88%) than soil type B (68%) of a previous study. This is attributed to the different type of analyzed conditions adopted by the researchers (3D nonlinear time history versus 2D quasi-static). However, a good agreement is achieved in the comparative fragility analysis proposed by Argyroudis et al. (2014) for both new and old circular tunnel (2D nonlinear analysis with SSI). This proved that although ignoring the effect of SSI, the proposed 3D models produced an acceptable results for nonlinear time history analysis (Hatzigeorgiou & Beskos 2010). The highest percentage of minor damages are predicted for the soil type C after 100 years of service time (Figs. 4.6 and 4.7). The derived fragility curve is predicted to experience higher percentage of minor damage compared to the judgmental fragility curves prepared by NIBS (2004). This can be attributed to the parameters of damping and stiffness of both types of soil (Fig. 4.8). Otherwise, based on Fig. 4.9, it is assumed that the proposed curve is under a good quality construction as compared to the empirical ones. It is also noted that, a better agreement is achieved since the proposed curve is buried in the rock medium.

5. CONCLUSION

A simple yet comprehensive numerical methodology is presented to construct fragility curves for shallow metro tunnels in rock medium, when subjected to transversal seismic loading. It is found that the surrounding soil plays an important role in evaluating the performance and response of the tunnel. The curves are modified due to different soil condition, while the judgmental and empirical curves rather describe an average response of the tunnels. The lowest percentage probability of tunnel damage occurs for well-constructed tunnels in good ground conditions, especially in stiff rock. However, it is of paramount importance not to overlook other uncertainty factors. Moreover, the definition of damage index, damage states and beta values can alter the obtained results. The purpose of the fragility curve is to make a preliminary assessment of tunnel response for different seismic scenarios. However, critical analyses are required to ensure that the proposed fragility curve is reliable to cover a major aspect of the study and might be useful to provide new knowledge for risk assessment and loss estimation.

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